

Towards A Global Cyber Architecture For Global Britain

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Beginning

As the most amorphous and dynamic realm, cyber is less a distinct domain and more a permeating field or medium that pervades and synergises with all other domains known and utilised by humans and machines. This paper explores the history, background, contemporary meanings, and use cases of cyber, cyberspace, and other related utilities. It then pursues an expansion of its conception beyond common concerns of discourse or operations, whether it be in the military, information technology, business, or politics. It argues that while all currently held viewpoints are crucial and accurate to a certain degree, it limits our understanding of the potential and eventual benefits of cyber as a notional and ethereal field of cognition, interaction, potentiality, and the existence of biological entities and physical objects or things, similar to that of modern field theory in quantum mechanics (Kreuzer, 2021). In doing so, (1) the possibilities for strategic differentiation in value creation on various sectors or endeavours, (2) the discourse relating to cyber political economy to aid in liberating purviews that allow utility beyond the constraints of being a military domain, a function of information system security, and as an economic or commercial arena of electronic exchanges, and finally (3) the planning for policy, governance, protocols, operations, product development, capability development, education, cross-sector innovation, and venture investment may vastly expand and diversify.

A Look To The Past For The Present And Future

From its etymology of the greek word “kybernetes” or steersman, as (1) a linguistic lemma of its earliest use as the field of cybernetics in 1948 coined by mathematician Norbert Wiener pertaining to the autonomous control or metaphorical steering of mechanical or biological systems (Lillemose & Kryger, 2015), (2) a Danish architectural concept for open and adaptable sensory spaces devoid of technology in the 1960s (Lillemose & Kryger, 2015) and (3) a science fiction phenomenon of the collective data bank of all computers in the system of humanity represented in graphical form in the 1980s authored by William Gibson in the short story *Burning Chrome* (Gibson, 1988) and *Neuromancer* (Gibson, 1984), cyber and cyberspace have encapsulated and have morphed into numerous conceptions and uses (Choucri, 2015; Ning et

al, 2018). This tradition continues to date as its semantic meaning has drifted and its contextual use in various disciplines has evolved to fit the interests of its diverse proponents, to serve specific public discourse, and to align with prevailing technological and socio-political paradigms (Choucri, 2015; Beecroft, 2021).

By and large, the definition of cyber and cyberspace, whether within the strategic uses of governments and military or in the commercial lifecycle of companies and enterprises, is centred around the representation in 3 areas: the Physical World, the Logical World, and the Social or Human World (Clark, 2010; Gao et al, 2019; Ministry of Defence, 2022b). There are additional descriptions that extend these 3 layers to include Personas on top of humans, a distinction between Information and Data at the Logical level, and additional sub-categorisation for Cyber-Enabled Spaces as opposed to purely physical constructs (Ning et al, 2018). Finally, recent discourse and research (Choucri, 2015; Clarke, 2010; Wren, 2015) are expanding these useful albeit sprawling definitions to include practical and operational considerations that are already in place in the industry and the real world. These include but are not limited towards the explicit inclusion of (1) communication mediums beyond TCP/IP or Transmission Control Protocol over Internet Protocol like SCADA or Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition and other emerging communications protocols used for Internet-of-Things deployments or Cyber-Physical Systems which are commonly referred by their acronym as IoT and CPS, respectively (Greer, et a, 2019; IETF, n.d.; Prince & Sullivan, 2019), (2) systems and software that provide operational consistency beyond hardware failures, (3) network and subnetworks, (4) access nodes, and (5) the data involved.

From a practitioner, social, and academic perspective, the emergent and contemporary consensus of cyber as a concept is that of a notional environment and digitisation of human existence, usually with dark undertones and sentiments (Bussell, 2013; Lillemose & Kryger, 2015). Despite this, a review of literature, strategy papers from the military and government of various countries, and other commercial domains shows the dominant function of cybersecurity as a premiere consideration above all else, in terms of importance, attention, investments, and productive use. This paper aims to propose and contribute to a countervailing force in the increasingly hijacked conception of cyber and cyberspace as a distinct domain of

operations (Cook et al, 2022; DCMS, 2022; Department of Defense, 2022) and as a limited discipline relating predominantly to cybersecurity (ICO, 2022). Cyber and cyberspace are better understood and cognitively organised as complex emergent phenomena (Martin & Helmersen, 2014), existing in a plane of abstraction and union set of related scientific and technical pre-conceptions to date.

Google Search Trends Weights	cyber: (1/7/18 - 1/7/23, United Kingdom)
Category / Subcategory	Weight
Cybercrime	100
Security	98
Computer security	96
Cyber Monday	48
Monday	47
Cyberattack	24
Cyberbullying	11
Bullying	10
Crime	10
Cyber Essentials	10
Course	8
Digimon Story: Cyber Sleuth	7
Black Friday	6
Cyberpunk 2077	6
Sony Cyber-shot	6
Sony	6
Risk Brilliant Math & Science Wiki	5
Computer	4
Apprenticeship	3
Tesla Cybertruck	3
Truck	3
Bachelor's degree	2
Pickup truck	2
Cyber Discovery	2
Engineer	2

Table 1: An Sampling Of Search Trends in Google Trends Tool for 'cyber' keyword (Google Trends, 2022)

Information sciences and technology share a fabled history with the United Kingdom. From the earliest mathematical conception of binary numerical systems to theoretical machines designed to automate and evaluate mathematical operations and algorithms (IISS, 2021), the UK and especially its people in collaboration with experts and scholars around the world laid the foundation of the digital age (Saran, 2016). This is reminiscent of the foundations of the Industrial Revolution in the UK, albeit with historical variations regarding how the UK gained

global dominance in the energy and manufacturing sector, within the context of imperial regime (Edwards, 2021). This is in contrast to the multipolar rise of creation, distribution, and commercialisation of information technologies worldwide in the present (Jazdi, 2014; Lloyds Bank, 2021). The UK indeed led in the invention and use cases of research- and government-centric computing machines and platforms. With the first universal computers, SSEM and EDSAC, that came to fore from Manchester and Cambridge Universities, respectively; and the ingenious team from Bletchley Park that blend mathematics, electrical engineering, computing theory, and other cryptographic genius, to thwart and intercept mind-boggling complex wartime enemy communications, there is a repeated testament that the tradition of intellect and determination to make things happen remain strong (Lavington, 2010; Science Museum, 2018).

Broad research of available literature and reports portray numerous superlatives and pre-eminence that the UK holds to the present (DCMS, 2022; House of Lords, 2022; Insider Studios & UK DTI, 2022; Nye, 2011; Steed, 2021; Turner, 2019). These span information and data points which advocate an open political environment an advanced developed economy, a sophisticated education, research, and development ecosystem, the home of many leading new enterprises especially in Europe, a dominant role in facing societal challenges like climate change, a principal player in global security and diplomacy, an outstanding global soft power (Nye, 2005) by many measures and standards in extending its influence, and several other accomplishments that give the impression that not much is to be done (House of Lords, 2022; Ministry of Defence, 2022a). Science and technology play a prominent role in the UK economy and are reputed as a force for research, development, and innovation across various sectors like biotechnology, finance, energy, and others (Holmes, 2022; House of Lords, 2022). In fact, by many standards, especially those that can be objectively measured by the amount of inbound foreign and domestic investments received, the UK, compared regionally and internationally, is either the leader or among the leaders in the league of economies partaking in relevant sectors. (Insider Studios & UK DTI, 2022).

The Mission

The call for evidence by the UK government, under the scope of the Integrated Review encompassing national security, military defence, international development, and foreign policy interests, encouraged a crucial mood and tone for the government that reflects the clear and present challenges facing the UK, its allies, and the world at large (HM Government, 2021). Moreover, it broadcasts a signal - beyond the deliberations, bickering, and machinations among various factions and interests - to people, businesses, institutions, and societies both domestic and abroad, of a concerted aim from the highest stratum of the government.

While any initiative and direction will have opposing parties and countervailing circumstantial forces that will create friction, sharpen its focus, compromise its arguments, derail its momentum, or undermine its chances for success, the ethos and principles establishing strategies, policies, and courses of action aiming for coherence, cohesion, multi-modality, and multi polarity among related groups is necessary. The challenges facing the UK and the world are overlapping and interconnected (Roubini, 2022a; Roubini, 2022b), notwithstanding the areas and degrees by which each will be affected may differ. The Global Strategic Trends (Ministry of Defence, 2022a) are identified in the UK spheres of influence like the military as (1) Increasing Human Empowerment, (2) Power Transition and Diffusion, (3) Centrality of Information, (4) Accelerating Technical Development, (5) Increasing Environmental Stress, and (6) Changing Populations and Evolving Habitats. Each trend presents realities that are both engendered by past actions and circumstances as well as emergent ones that have had no precedent we can draw lessons from. These represent, in often equal measure, a challenge to be addressed but also an opportunity that can be capitalised on for future progress (Jordan et al, 2016).

A Conceptual Architecture

The architectural diagram depicted in Figure 1 portrays a proposed conceptual baseline design for what constitutes an emergent cyberspace. It depicts contextual components involved in its existence and the concerns that are typically assessed in cyber-related strategies, operations, finance, and research. While it is admittedly constrained in portraying the all-encompassing context in full depth; for example, the consideration for sector-specific needs, additional details on scientific and technical considerations, and other activities relating to day-to-day integration with human life. It orients itself towards enforcing the standpoint that cyber is not confined as (1) a military domain or sphere of operation or as (2) a cybersecurity function alone. Respectively, these are intersecting and orthogonal considerations in possibly a third dimension of this diagram as well as a crucial but component factor consideration only across various layers of abstractions and considerations.

The architecture depicts layers of actors and intervening connectivity modalities that link to the boundary of cyberspace which this paper proposes to be formally called Cyber Temporal Activation Nexus and Event Horizon. It harks back to fundamental physical laws of time and space as well as potentiality and kinetic existence. For example, an internet-enabled mobile device, in and of itself, while imbued with all the abilities for interactivity with its environment via sensors and human-computer interaction components including the ability to connect to cyberspace via the Internet through an intervening 5G mobile network, does not exist in cyberspace. Until its data and information flow, it only has the potential to be so. Once this energy, information, and data does flow in interaction with other abstracted data flow does it become part of the emergent cyberspace itself. Underpinning this is a counterpart boundary logically facing the physical infrastructure and other abstraction layers that enable connectivity to cyber. Cross-concerns like logistics, security, intelligence, governance, compliance, assurance, policies and standards form part of its value chain and governance oversight. Technical facets like physical hardware, software, operating environments, applications, and integrations of components are supporting structures enabling every aspect of the cyber continuum.

A common and comprehensive doctrine is crucial as it allows more stakeholders to partake in dialogue and joint engagements. Additionally, it encourages an expansive set of possibilities that can be weighed for pursuit in a measured, risk-adjusted, and contextualised manner. As a tool for change, command, and education, the conceptual architecture hopes to become part of doctrine to ensure that assessments, debates, experiments, operations, and transformation initiatives in the government, the military, foreign affairs, commercial interests, and society as a whole will be based in enduring principles, known good practices, historical lessons, on the ground experience, and analytical objective ethos. As such, dependence on varying priorities and interests across government people and policy churn can be minimised.

Figure 1: A Conceptual Architecture of Cyberspace

Broad. Integrated. Deep. Supported.

Strategy is a concept and endeavour that is both used very formally and loosely but rarely in coherently distinct activities and purposes, even within the same context and culture. The UK has a preponderance of strategies, frameworks, and action plans (DCMS, 2022; Ministry of Defence, 2022a). Prevailing practices distinguish strategies vs planning by the rational and differentiation for succeeding in a competitive context vs a set of defined activities, respectively (Martin, 2022). There are numerous factors involved from the interplay of the military and the economy (Smith, 2008), the constraint of budget and finance, the opinions and convictions of various schools of thought and other considerations relating to the political climate, socio-economic situation at any given point in time, the technological realities that enable or catalyses changes, the environmental impact of strategy, and the legal frameworks that give structure to the rules of engagement among actors.

Rank	2020	2022
1	US	US
2	China	China
3	UK	Russia
4	Russia	UK
5	Netherlands	Australia
6	France	Netherlands
7	Germany	ROK
8	Canada	Vietnam
9	Japan	France
10	Australia	Iran

Table 2: National Cyber Power Index (Voo et al, 2022)

In understanding strategy and approaching the challenge in a manner that is broad, integrated, deep, and supported as the situation rightfully demands, a dilemma emerged as contrasting views in literature, institutional reports, public opinion news and fora, and other statistics portray both the ‘great’ and ‘global’ in the UK (Brand Finance, 2022; British Academy, 2022; Holmes, 2022; House of Lords, 2022; Voo et al, 2022) while from another perspective

economic realities and data demonstrate dire and difficult situations faced by the UK, at the individual level or at the national and international arena. This divergence persists even when adjusted for the UK's country peers and other relevant leading and trailing indicators that provide evidence that the UK is facing multi-faceted and inter-related challenges like (1) labour shortages for varying skills level, (2) declining trade posture, (3) regressing productivity indices and investment portfolio, (4) persistent supply chain challenges, (5) tourism and cultural deficits, (6) science funding cuts, (7) the UK falling last compared to G7 peers, (8) declining social-economic progress indices across nearly all attributes like water quality, racial harmony, healthcare challenges, educational standards, human rights, and others (Green et al, 2022), and (9) a lagging position in key diplomacy indices trailing Russia, Turkey, Japan, France, United States, and China (Green et al, 2022; Heritage Foundation, 2022; Inman, 2022).

An exploration of publicly available discussions and official responses to the call for evidence of the Integrated Review yields materials that broadly outline, among other things the need for more budget at par with peers (OECD, 2022), investment in strategic sciences like AI and biotechnology to achieve science superpower status however they may have defined it, broader coalitions within national and international parties, and projecting that the UK is a force for good. There are myriads of strategies and frameworks (DCMS, 2022; Ministry of Defence, 2022a) touted publicly and among government groups to lack clear targets and action plans on one end or are too ambitious or trivial at the other end of the spectrum (Ministry of Defence, 2022a, House of Lords, 2022).

It can be argued though that finance, investment, and sweeping support across strategic fundamental capabilities is a given: the military needs the economy; the economy needs the military and government (Smith, 2008); spending and budgets cannot simply be switched off (Thies & Baum, 2020; Tian et al, 2020); soft diplomacy needs 'hard' presence and action (Lowy Institute, 2021); international development needs resilient economies which in term needs good international standing (Anholt, 2020); and other competing forces that needs consideration but are first principles, so to speak. The debate is in the policies, methods, and mechanisms for executing plans, not whether crucial plans may optionally exist. What is or are the veritable spectrum of problems when everything is uncertain or in flux? What point is there

for the demanded clear, specific, and measurable targets in 3 months, 6 months, 12 months, or 2 years and beyond with rapid cycles of political and policy churn as well as a global trend ever veering towards permacrisis and polycrisis (Derbyshire, 2023)

Recent sectoral analysis, in particular but is not limited to cyber sector, shows prioritisation is ruled mostly by military cyber defence and offence as well as commercial investment interests centred around cybersecurity companies with very granular fields of productisation (Rosemont, 2021; Steed, 2021; Stevens & O'Brien, 2019). Apart from this, investment expectations for companies are clubbed singularly towards unicorn potentialities, or companies that have billion-dollar market capitalisation, regardless of other financial fundamentals like breadth, depth, scale, and sustainability of the new enterprise or startup (Edwards, 2021). This is understandable from a venture capitalist perspective, no matter how its preferences may be configured; the ethos and investment strategies are diverse, flexible, and subjective. The role of government, apart from its ultimate sovereign power to create the environment, policies, regulations, and enforcement by which companies and institutions operate are to balance hindsight, insight, and foresight as well as being able to encourage a variety of time horizon and programme risk profile beyond what the private sector can provide (CERN, 2016; CERN, 2018; Cordesman, 2022; DCMS, 2022; Holmes, 2022; Kugler, 1994).

Another encouraging tale tinged perhaps by lessons of missing out and lack of productive oversight, we view two important entities in the computing industry globally: Tim Berners Lee and ARM. Their respective story, contributions, and successes can nearly run parallel to the story of the success and progress of the modern cyberspace that we have today. Berners-Lee invented the World Wide Web referred to simply as WWW while working in the European Organization for Nuclear Research or CERN (CERN, 2019). ARM is the descendant of Acorn Computers (Hern, 2015).

Founded in Cambridge, Acorn Computers dealt in low-power and accessible computers for educational purposes and other casual uses. (Bloom, 2021; Hern, 2015). Over its history, it discovered the Reduced Instruction Set Computer processor design from University of California Berkeley. Its fundamental design was typified by its simplified processing routines at

the most basic level to reduce interrupt latency thereby significantly reducing its baseline power consumption. This characteristic will become a crucial stepping stone in its design excellence, starting with Acorn Risc Machines (ARM) which eventually became its corporate name. Its business model included royalties in design work, opening the possibility for repeatable revenues. This will become the cornerstone of its success as a ubiquitous presence in modern personal mobile devices as well as other embedded systems requiring low power and specialised designs. It has been the subject of corporate takeovers in Japan via a telecommunications giant and the US via a leading graphics processor manufacturer. ARM has been reported numerous times to have difficulties beneficial support in the UK, either through its Initial Public Offering in the London Stock Exchange as well as general investment support for its expansion (Makortoff, 2022). It was at some point worth 55 billion US dollars.

While more detailed discussions of the technical and engineering standards of the Internet are outside the purview of this paper, it must be stated that the Internet, cyberspace, and the WWW are three but distinct conceptual constructs. Simplistically, the Internet is the inter-networking of various distributed networks to create a system without a single point of failure; the WWW is an application of information science and technology to share and link documents and information in a standard way over an existing network and related protocols, e.g. intranets over ethernet, TCP/IP, and other networking modalities (Science Museum, 2018). Cyberspace and cyber, in essence, and as proposed in this paper, is a general and portable phenomenon that emerges from pervasive and persistent networks with data and information constantly going through its physical and logical systems, akin to blood flowing through the circulatory systems of complex biological entities; i.e. a body with complete organs but with blood carrying energy and other essential elements not flowing, there is no emergence of the phenomenon of life. All modern use cases in the internet across various sectors can trace its lineage in one form or another to the enablement provided by WWW including succeeding standards and innovations it directly and indirectly enabled (Jazdi, 2014); without it, perhaps the Internet would not have been as universally useful as it is today (Greer et al, 2019, IAB, 2021;).

The purpose of the above discourse is not merely history, but to outline a pattern and context of UK inventions, innovations, and ingenuity whose maximal potential was not achieved; opportunities while never certain in the beginning, were evidenced by their success outside the UK; e.g. (1) early computing innovations that could have spawned the early IT revolution instead of commercial benefits predominantly finding its dominant home in other economies (IAB, 2021; Saran, 2016); Tim Berners-Lee found progress, support, and stimulating environment not in the UK (CERN, 2019); ARM found larger support, interest, and partnerships also outside the UK (Bloom, 2021; Hern, 2015; Makortoff, 2022).

An enterprising Critical National Capability Continuum which includes cyber, space, emerging technologies, mature operational circumstances, and other evolving configurations of governance, strategy, planning, operations, and transformation needs to be crafted and widely distributed for education and feedback. This continuum structurally mirrors a Hype Cycle that views the swath of capabilities that are in play within its technological, innovation, and utility lifecycle from its (1) Trigger, (2) Peak of Inflated Expectation, (3) Trough of Disillusionment, (4) Slope of Enlightenment, and (5) Plateau of Productivity (Dedehayir & Steinert, 2016; Eger & Drukker, 2010; Lajoie & Bridges, 2014).

This continuum is integrated with an angel investment or venture capital mindset, but with broader time horizons and categorical breadth, integration, depth, and supporting structures, uninhibited by short-termism (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Risk management and continuum situational awareness is an ongoing cross-functional activity, providing guidance rather than purely a veto power.

Conclusion

Ultimately, in war, we long for peace; in peace, we prepare for and long for war (Sun Tzu, 1981; Von Clausewitz, 2021). While specific interests vary and actors change, the essential endeavour and reality of war and peace will embody aspects of political and economic aspirations and constraints.

But to what end are all these schemes, strategies and plans for, one may ask? The academic, intellectual, political, social, and technological branching out from classical and practical political economy may have created a proliferation of perceptions outside the realm of academe and politics. Jovially, ask a hundred scholars what political economy is and one gets a thousand interpretations. It can be argued, though, that as politics, policy, and power ultimately create the necessary environment by which economies and societies operate and progress more than any criteria like history, culture, technology, and other meta-structures (Chang, 2003), it is more important than ever to make the field of political economy accessible and understandable by the common person. In non-objective reflection, the best introduction in literature and book reviews so far is one authored by perhaps one of the most unsung figures of political economy, Millicent Garrett Fawcett in 1870. In her modestly titled book but whose impact is definitely not trivial, *Political Economy for Beginners* (Fawcett, 2004), the first line of the first chapter started with:

Political Economy is the science which investigates the nature of wealth, and the laws which govern its Production, Exchange and Distribution. As wealth is the subject of political economy it is necessary to understand precisely what wealth is. Wealth is anything which has an exchange value.

Wealth though means many things to many parties. It is subjective, contextual, and changeable. This is the crux of the arguments humbly put forward by this paper, be it in the technical conceptions of cyber or in planning for an uncertain future political, social, military, institutional, and personal economy: a counter-rigidity and antifragility in the ethos of our endeavours, the diligent expansion of conceptualisation to sympathetically capture a wider cross-section of milieu, the acceptance of lessons in hindsight, the intelligence of insight, the enterprising spirit of foresight that pursues with humility in meeting failures, responsible planning with measured risk not recklessness, the appreciation of historical privileges and entitlements but ever ready to discard its comforting complacencies, and the concerted and

unified front while ever-changing in its composition remains steadfast and unwavering. Naivete, surely; but perhaps this is what is needed to make the ideas and ideals for Global Britain a reality.

Annex

	Total	Swiss share
Member States' Contribution (2019)	1,174.6 million CHF	47.1 million CHF (4.0 %)
CERN expenditure on orders and contracts ¹ (2019)	482.4 million CHF	108.7 million CHF (22.5 %) spent in Switzerland
Employees ² (2020)	3,391	957 with residence in Switzerland (28.2 %)
Visiting scientists, users, students etc. (2019/2020)	14,233	1,626 with residence in Switzerland (11.4 %)

Table 3: Quick Summary of CERN in Switzerland (CERN, 2016)

Cost _A		Benefits _A	
Swiss CERN contribution	47 million CHF	CERN expenditures	109 million CHF
		Net consumption	209 million CHF
		Staff/fellows/students (741/216/53)	55 million CHF
		Users ²⁴ (1,418)	39 million CHF
		Other MPA (156)	6 million CHF
		Visitors (151,681)	72 million CHF
		Pensioners (715)	36 million CHF
Tax exemptions	20 million CHF	Tax revenue	28 million CHF
VAT	0.2 million CHF	VAT ²⁵	10 million CHF
Income tax	20 million CHF	Income Tax	18 million CHF
Interest on loans	1.7 million CHF		
Lease of land	7 million CHF		
TOTAL	75 million CHF	TOTAL	345 million CHF
Gross effect: 270 million CHF			
Benefits-cost-ratio: 4.6			
Direct employment effects²⁶: 2,583			

Table 4: Cost Benefit Model of CERN for Switzerland, Low Estimate Method (CERN. 2016)

Cost _B		Benefits _B	
Swiss CERN contribution	47 million CHF	PSI expenditure	12 million CHF
		Avg. industry exp.	323 million CHF
		Net consumption	58 million CHF
		Employees (avg. Industry) (1,343)	45 million CHF
		Staff (PSI) (259)	12 million CHF
		Users (PSI) (381)	0.2 million CHF
		Tax revenue	46 million CHF
		VAT	2 million CHF
		Income Tax	10 million CHF
		Corporate income tax	33 million CHF
		Lease of land	6 million CHF
TOTAL	47 million CHF	TOTAL	445 million CHF
Gross effect: 398 million CHF			
Benefits-cost-ratio: 9.5			
Direct Employment Effects²³: 1,602			

Table 5: Cost Benefit Model of CERN for Switzerland, High Estimate Method (CERN, 2016)

Figure 2: United Kingdom Global Diplomacy Index (Lowy Institute, 2021)

Figure 3: China Global Diplomacy Index (Lowy Institute, 2021)

Figure 4: USA Global Diplomacy Index (Lowy Institute, 2021)

Hype Cycle for Digital Government Services, 2022

gartner.com

Source: Gartner
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Figure 5: Hype Cycle for Digital Government Services, 2022 (Perri, 2022)

List of Abbreviations

ACD	Active Cyber Defence
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
BEIS	Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy
CAF	Cyber Assessment Framework
CBO	Congressional Budget Office
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological and Nuclear
CERN	European Centre for Nuclear Research / Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
CIA	Central Intelligence Agency
CJEF	Combined Joint Expeditionary Force
CK	Crypt-Key
CO	Cabinet Office
COBR	Cabinet Office Briefing Rooms
CPTPP	Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership
CPS	Cyber-physical system
CNI	Critical national infrastructure
CS	Cyberspace
CT	Counter-terrorism
CTOC	Counter Terrorism Operations Centre
CyBOK	Cyber Security Body of Knowledge

DARPA	US Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency
DCMS	Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport
DSTL	Defence Science and Technology Laboratory
EU	European Union
FCAS	Future combat air system
FCDO	Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office
FDI	Foreign direct investment
FPDA	Five Power Defence Arrangements
FTA	Free trade agreement
GAO	Government Accountability Office (US government auditors)
GC	General cyberspace
GCCC	Government Cyber Coordination Centre
GCHQ	Government Communications Headquarters
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GFCE	Global Forum on Cyber Expertise
GNI	Gross national income
GPS	Global Positioning System
HO	Home Office
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICANN	Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers
ICS	Industrial Control System
ICT	Information and communications technology

LRF	Local resilience forum
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IoT	Internet of Things
IOSM	In Orbit Servicing and Manufacturing
IT	Information Technology
JFCyG	Joint Forces Cyber Group
MoD	UK Ministry of Defence
NAO	National Audit Office (UK government auditors)
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
NCA	National Crime Agency
NCF	National Cyber Force
NCSC	National Cyber Security Centre
NCSP	National Cyber Security Programme
NCSS	National Cyber Security Strategy
NECC	National Economic Crime Centre
NIS	Network and Information Systems
NOCP	National Offensive Cyber Programme
NSC	National Security Council
NSRA	National Security Risk Assessment
ODA	Official Development Assistance
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OSCE	Organisation for Security and Co-operation in Europe

OT	Operational Technologies
PST	Physical, Social, and Thinking spaces
RAF	Royal Air Force
R&D	Research and development
RUSI	Royal United Services Institute, the oldest military think-tank
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SIPRI	Stockholm International Peace Reserch Institute
SIS	Secret Intelligene Service - also known as MI6
SNS	Social network services
SOC	Serious and organised crime
SR	Spending Review
S&T	Science and Technology
UN	United Nations
WTO	World Trade Organisation

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